

Study of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) with some Reactive Methylene Compounds and Carboxylic Acids by Polarography

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Schaap and McMasters method has been used to determine the overall formation constants of mixed ligand complexes formed by Cu^{II} with tartrate-*N*-(2-ethoxy)phenyl malonamate and with tartrate-*N*-(2-chloro)phenyl malonamate systems. DeFord and Hume's treatment shows that Cu^{II} forms two complex species each with tartrate, *N*-(2 ethoxy) phenyl malonamate and *N*-(2 chloro)phenyl malonamate. In both mixed ligand systems, one mixed complex of the type Cu[X][Y] is formed.

Schaap and McMasters¹ extended DeFord and Hume's² method to apply to cases where a metal ion forms complex with two ligands simultaneously in solution. There have been a number of studies on mixed ligand complex formation³. In continuation with our earlier studies⁴ on mixed ligand complexes, the present report deals with copper-tartrate(tart)-*N*-(2-ethoxy)phenyl malonamate (EPM) and copper-tart-*N*-(2-chloro)phenyl malonamate (CPM) systems.

Results and Discussion

Simple systems : The formation constants of the complexes of Cu^{II} with tartrate, *N*-(2-ethoxy)-phenyl malonamate and *N*-(2-chloro)phenyl malonamate were measured separately under identical conditions. In all the systems, Cu^{II} produced a single well-defined wave. The plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ were linear and passed through origin. The plots of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $E_{d.o.}$ were linear with a slope of (31 ± 1) mV. Thus, the reduction processes were diffusion-controlled and reversible involving two electrons.

The overall formation constants of simple complexes have been evaluated by DeFord and Hume's method and the values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR SINGLE LIGAND COMPLEXES

$\mu=2.0$	
Complex species	Formation constants
[Cu(Tart)]	$\log \beta_1 = 3.38$
[Cu(Tart) ₂] ²⁻	$\log \beta_2 = 5.56$
[Cu(EPM)] ⁺	$\log \beta_1 = 5.77$
[Cu(EPM) ₂]	$\log \beta_2 = 8.52$
[Cu(CPM)] ⁺	$\log \beta_1 = 5.41$
[Cu(CPM) ₂]	$\log \beta_2 = 7.96$

Mixed systems : The Cu-tart-EPM and Cu-tart-CPM systems were studied by keeping the concentration of weaker ligand constant (0.0005 M) while varying the stronger ligand (tart) concentration. A shift in half-wave potential to more negative values with increase in tartrate concentration was observed. This shift was greater in the presence of weaker ligand (EPM or CPM) than in its absence, which signified mixed ligand formation. The Schaap and McMasters treatment was applied to the $E_{1/2}$ data and F_{00} functions evaluated.

Leden's graphical extrapolation method⁵ was then applied to calculate *A*, *B* and *C* (details of calculations are given in Tables 2 and 3). In both the systems, copper formed one mixed complexes each, [Cu(Tart)(EPM)]⁻, [Cu(Tart)(CPM)]⁻ having $\log \beta_{1,1}$ as 7.71 and 7.08 respectively. The various equilibria existing in solutions are presented in Schemes 1 and 2. The numerical values represent $\log K$, where *K* is the equilibrium constant of the step indicated in the summary.

TABLE 2—Cu^{II}-TARTRATE-*N*-(2-ETHOXY)PHENYL MALONAMATE SYSTEM

[Cu^{II}]= 1×10^{-3} M, $\mu=2.0$ (KNO₃), pH=6.0, Temp = 25 ± 0.1°, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.1 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$, $h_{\text{corr}}=55.6$ cm, ($E_{1/2}$)_s = -0.015 V (vs S.C.E.)

[Tart ²⁻] M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	F_{00} [X,Y]	F_{10} [X,Y] $\times 10^{-2}$	F_{20} [X,Y] $\times 10^{-2}$
0.005	15.32	0.045	31	10.56	—	—
0.010	15.01	0.055	32	23.44	—	—
0.020	14.62	0.079	30	156.02	74.01	—
0.030	14.50	0.093	31	468.01	156.00	3.5
0.040	13.94	0.100	30	840.00	208.00	3.9
0.050	12.94	0.104	31	1235.50	245.50	3.9
0.060	12.80	0.108	32	1700.06	282.01	3.8

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

TABLE 3—Cu^{II}-TARTRATE-N-(2-CHLORO)PHENYL MALONAMATE SYSTEM

$[\text{Cu}^{II}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 2.0$ (KNO₃), pH=6.0, Temp.=25 ± 0.1°, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.1 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$, $k_{\text{corr}} = 55 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, $(E_{1/2})_s = -0.015 \text{ V}$ (vs S.C.E.)

$[\text{Tart}^{2-}]$ M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	F_{00} [X,Y]	F_{10} [X,Y] $\times 10^{-2}$	F_{20} [X,Y] $\times 10^{-5}$
0.005	16.56	0.054	31	21.14	—	—
0.010	16.30	0.071	30	80.02	71.02	4.1
0.020	16.00	0.087	32	285.49	138.24	5.4
0.030	15.16	0.096	30	607.85	199.61	5.6
0.040	15.10	0.103	32	1 052.93	260.98	5.7
0.050	14.12	0.109	31	1 558.68	309.53	5.6
0.060	13.86	0.112	32	2 309.93	383.48	5.8

The equilibrium constants (log value) for the following disproportionation reactions,

and

work out to be -1.34 and -0.64 . The negative values indicate that the formation of mixed complex is strongly favoured over the simple ones.

The mixing constants (K_M) for the reactions, $1/2[\text{Cu}(\text{Tart})_2] + 1/2[\text{Cu}(\text{EPM})_2] \rightleftharpoons [\text{Cu}(\text{Tart})(\text{EPM})]^-$ and

are given by the relation,

$$\log K_M = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02}]$$

and work out to be 0.67 and 0.32 respectively. The positive log values show that mixed complexes are somewhat more stable than the binary complexes.

Experimental

Sodium salts of tartaric acid, *N*-(2-ethoxy)phenyl malonamic acid and *N*-(2-chloro)phenylmalonamic acid were used as complexing agents. KNO₃ was used as supporting electrolyte ($\mu = 2.0$). All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The polarographic measurements were made with a manual set-up. The potential measurements made with respect to SCE and the dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics in open circuit: $m = 2.4048 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t = 3.4 \text{ s}$. The pH measurements were

made on a Toshniwal pH-meter. A constant temperature was maintained ($25 \pm 0.1^\circ$) throughout the investigation.

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